

Why is it useful to add discoverability to an online music marketing strategy?

Breaking through the recommendation echo chamber to stimulate the discoverability and export of sound recordings: analysis of the relationship between enriched metadata and global streaming listening.

Findings and preliminary report

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Introduction: context and issues of the research project

Why is it useful to add discoverability to an online music marketing strategy ?

This report reflects work on the subject undertaken from March 2022 to October 2024. Since the topics of discoverability and digital technologies applied to recorded music are still evolving and rapidly, our research protocols have also evolved and will continue to do so.

For this project, I first benefited from funding from the Mitacs program as a doctoral student and co-director of the Research Laboratory on Discoverability and Transformations of Cultural Industries in the Era of Electronic Commerce (LATICCE) which partnered with Jacynthe Plamondon's Quebec independent production and management company InTempo Musique.

The project received additional funding in January 2023 through the Franco-Quebec strategy on discoverability of cultural content online (Quebec, Ministry of Culture and Communications and France Ministry of Culture, 2020) and has revised its objectives in order to broaden its reach to artists in France. It has entered into partnerships with MetaMusic in Quebec, La FELIN, LabEx ICCA and Musicoverly in France.

The project aims to try to understand and act on the filter bubbles associated with online music listening profiles by using enriched metadata sets that artists and labels control and which are not always exploited by platform recommendation systems.

It is an **action research** project which relies on both numerical measurement methods using Music Tomorrow statistical tools, Chartmetric, InTempo Analytics, Hercules Report and on the **mobilization of knowledge** lived by labels impacted by the realities of streaming music on a daily basis.

It is a project carried out in Quebec (Canada) and in France and which uses some of the observable differences in the behavior of actors and market conditions in the two territories to verify its hypotheses and results.

The work is carried out along four axes:

1. the study of streaming services and market players;
2. statistical measurement BEFORE and AFTER product enrichment (on which this preliminary report focuses);
3. the definition of best business practices (to come);
4. the study of economic impacts for artists and labels (to come).

The project benefited from the contribution of around ten researchers and stakeholders from the music industry and nearly a hundred artists and labels. Over time, these numbers may increase to reflect more scenarios and realities.

The current preliminary report describes the issues and considerations associated with **the establishment of a product enrichment measurement protocol**.

Finally, I would like to emphasize that at this stage of research, and according to the agreed formula, this report is solely the responsibility of its author.

What do we really know about discoverability?

Discoverability offers a techno-solutionist, at times utopian, response to the situation marked by the unlimited quantity of available content and the limits of the attention time that humans can devote to music listening. Artists will ask themselves : How can I make sure my music is heard?

Before we can offer an answer to this thorny question, we know with certainty that if a digitized music file is not documented using metadata, its authors and performers, its producers, its record label and quantity of other information will escape those who listen and problems will arise regarding the payment of royalties.

Services like YouTube, Apple Music or Spotify require that be delivered to them some of this information to allow the addition of titles to their service. This is the case for the ISRC and ISNI codes (increasingly) which identify registrations, people, organizations and help attribute the sums payable to them.

The question that arises today is whether this documentation can also allow artists to better reach their audiences.

In 2020, France and Quebec published a [joint discoverability report](#)¹ and launched a call for research projects in 2022 to rule on this question.

The report you are holding is the result of work supported by this initiative.

Following the example of France which adopted, at the end of 2023, a policy of taxation of streaming platforms to contribute to the financing of the sector through support for the National Music Center (CNM), Canada adopted a new Online Streaming Act (Bill C-11) in 2024.

Canadian law not only provides for a contribution to the financing of new productions by the platforms, but introduces the idea that they should undertake measures to ensure the *discoverability of original Canadian broadcasts*. The concept of broadcasts here covers the notion of original Canadian musical works, particularly in French and Indigenous languages.²

What Canada is trying to do is regulate how its artists are showcased online by imposing discoverability obligations on platforms.

It seems interesting to consider the idea that documentation produced by artists and labels could help facilitate listening to a greater diversity of music and help platforms comply with possible regulations.

This report seeks to help support artists, labels and platforms in this documentation work which aims to improve the experience of listening to music online.

¹ To download in PDF: <https://numerique.banq.qc.ca/patrimoine/details/52327/4246653>

² Let us remember that in Canada, these communities are minorities and that their culture is often drowned out in the plethora of services.

The first Discoverability Measuring initiatives of LATICCE

Being able to measure discoverability and its impacts is essential to justify increased documentation work efforts.

LATICCE produced in 2019 a prototype measure of discoverability (PVR) which is based on the equation where P indicates presence, V indicates visibility and R, recommendation³. The recommendation itself is broken down into (c) concordance, (r) relevance and (n) novelty.

This work attempts not to measure the consumption of digital streams as we do to establish a commercial ranking, but rather to measure the actions taken by services to expose certain content to certain audiences.

The index is a measurement fixed over time which does not indicate an absolute level of discoverability, but rather allows us to see the progress and setbacks of the recommendation tools offered by the platforms. It is a tool that gauges the success of the recommendation in order to support new best practices among artists and labels⁴.

To produce these measurements and determine the index, we used personas and behavioral scenarios imitating user-subscribers to the services.

Definitions of discoverability

“Discoverability is the ability of cultural content to be **easily discovered by the consumer who is looking for it** and to **have it offered to the consumer who did not know of its existence**. » (official definition of discoverability, OCCQ, 2017, cited by Rioux et al., 2019)

This very widespread definition is also based on two complementary variables which are the concepts of findability (F) and adoption (A, sometimes identified as consumption (C)) and which are added to the PVR.

At Spotify, the concepts associated with discoverability are described as discovery journeys⁵. Findability corresponds to the notion of “**Made by You**” where the subscriber, through his proactive behavior (*Active Audience*), knows what he is looking for, finds it and adds it to his preferences. Visibility matches the route “**Made by Editors**” when the content is highlighted by the platform's editorialization processes which can be human, algorithmic or hybrid; finally, the routes “**Made for You**” are generated by algorithms based on the listening history and taste profiling of each subscriber.

Allowing to **discover content that you know** implies that the platform offers to query their inventory using as many tools and criteria as possible. For the moment, subscription listening platforms offer a rather basic search for musical pieces using the criteria of title (song and album), artist, lists of genres and listening context (Spotify).

Why is it not possible to query the inventory of streaming platforms by more keywords as it is possible to do for an organic Google search?

Ideally, subscribers could search in the soundtrack of a film, with the name of an artistic producer or studio engineer, the name of a label⁶, a recording studio, a city, a mood or by an expression in everyday language.

As for the question of **offering a track to someone who did not know it existed**, it underlines the importance of asking oneself whether the proposal will effectively target its recipient and will result in adoption. Will I make a recommendation, a discovery, an habit, will I integrate it to my playlists, to my favorite tracks?

³ Rioux et al. 2021: https://ieim.uqam.ca/spip.php?page=article-ceim&id_article=13145

⁴ Read more in chapter 9 of the book *Musique et données* (p. 85-99) published in 2023 by the Centre National de la Musique. <https://cnmlab.fr/recueil/musique-et-donnees/chapitre/9/>

⁵ Voir le guide Spotify for Artists - Made to be Found, https://found.byspotify.com/intro?utm_medium=homecard and Understanding recommendations on Spotify: <https://www.spotify.com/be-fr/safetyandprivacy/understanding-recommendations>

⁶ As such, it is possible to query Spotify by label, but this is a hidden function: e.g. label: "Motown"

This animated visualization, added for fun, illustrates the dynamics that characterize the adoption of a new product and is taken from an article by John Sterman (2001) *Systems dynamics modeling: tools for learning in a complex world*, California management review, Vol 43 no 1. Source : Wikimedia Commons : https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Adoption_SFD_ANI_s.gif

To activate the discoverability of music

Our project poses the postulate that if your music is better documented, this can only have positive effects in the more or less long term on the improvement of the tools supporting discoverability.

We put forward the hypothesis that there are people who listen to your music and want to know the context of it. They are not passive subscribers. We believe that various elements of context, such as instrumentation, contributors, keywords linked to a track, will allow algorithmic recommendation and artificial intelligence to come, through a causal effect, to guide the choices of subscribers in a way which is more respectful of the complexity of artistic proposals.

The question that arises, however, is when such documentation efforts will deliver real results for labels and artists already struggling with dizzying workloads.

So, to get there...

We believe in the importance of promoting real collaboration between platforms and labels.

We support the idea that competition will be played out *eventually*, between labels which will apply good business practices, which will succeed in associating enriched metadata with their content, and those which won't⁷.

We support the idea of incentivizing platforms to enable subscriber interactions with the algorithm, offering discoveries based on aesthetic or qualitative information provided by labels and artists.

"The relationship between Man and tool has become a relationship between tool and Man."
(Ivan Illich, 1973, cited by Marc Dugain in Adrien Rivière, 2024)

⁷ As a guide, see this job description for an Assistant Metadata Manager at Universal Music in South Africa... <https://www.musicinafrica.net/magazine/open-call-universal-music-metadata-and-release-assetproduction-assistant-sa> - Universal Music metadata and release asset/production assistant

User-centered or Artist-label-catalog-centered?

The discoverability of content is largely based on the continuum of actions taken by the actors in the creation and value chain of an artistic production sector like that of music. Ultimately, our goal is, by measuring it, to check whether this music reaches its audience. These measurements and observations among downstream subscribers are variables centered on the user or *user-centric*. Effective discoverability, usage or consumption data are located at the end of the value chain cursor.

However, for this content to reach users, we must look at the variables which are located at the start of the cursor of the value chain and which ensure that they are delivered adequately and that they are findable, visible, discoverable. These variables will be observable upstream, in different ways depending on the tracks and directories. We will tend to credit or accuse the algorithms as responsible for the good or bad performance in discoverability of content upstream, from the point of view centered on the artist, on the repertoire, or *artist-label-catalog-centric*.

Some will affirm that artificial intelligence processes can, in the long term, adequately bring a work closer to its target, relying strictly on an automatic, mathematical or statistical approach.

We support the idea that it is still important to identify the repertoire on which our assessment of recommendation and discoverability relates and that the recordings should optimally be prepared before their delivery to the platforms. We will call this the **pre-conditioning** or the activation of the potential discoverability, upstream, of an artist-label-repertoire centered angle.

What do we really know about Echo Chambers?

Eli Pariser in his work *The Filter Bubble : What The Internet Is Hiding From You*⁸ published more than ten years ago, conducted a major survey of scientists responsible for developing the recommendation functions of platforms, notably at Google. It identifies three key characteristics of echo chambers arising from the algorithmic calculations that first interact with your personal data: the individual is always alone in their echo chamber, the parameters of their echo chamber are invisible and they do not choose whether or not to enter an echo chamber.

The phenomenon of echo chambers or filter bubbles occurs when the recommendation systems of streaming services force listeners into more or less closed sound universes because they are conditioned by algorithms and their voluntary or involuntary biases.

Furthermore, there is no systematic correlation between the effective discoverability of a given directory and the existence of echo chambers. These two phenomena are subjective and linked to user expectations. The creation of a bubble based on the tastes of the subscriber can in fact contribute to their discovery and adoption of new similar artists that they do not yet know (*user-centric* issue). For the artist, however, the question arises of being associated with the trends of his choice, with similar artists who seem most appropriate to him, with whom he has real affinities (*artist-centric* issue).

The phenomenon of echo chambers should be analyzed according to the two scenarios, both *user-centered* and *artist-centered*. Our project is firstly interested in the artistic posture, it attempts to determine which levers these can use to gain control over the platforms.

From the point of view of artists, echo chambers, by enclosing listeners in very personalized bubbles, fragment audiences and, as a result, expose them to new proposals although very specific by virtue of what they listen to already. These new proposals may be restricted aesthetically but potentially less so geographically or the opposite. Thus, they can both favor or disadvantage discovery, depending on what the expectations are.

The echo chamber phenomenon is largely attributable to collaborative filtering, social data held by the platforms, and a technology already present in the very first recommendation algorithms.⁹, let's think about Amazon and the formula "*Customers who saw this item also saw...*" and it is still widely used today.

We note that, unlike Quebec, the phenomenon of filter bubbles, associated with collaborative filtering, is much less critical in France, a country with a stronger demographic, very populous neighboring countries and frequented by artists with a strong international reputation. However, for French people who wish to export to atypical territories, the issues of bubbles will still be present. For Quebecers, the

⁸ In free translation: The filter bubble: What the Internet hides from you

⁹ Watch Brian Whitman's classic (2012) *How music recommendation works — and doesn't work*, French translation by Jean-Robert Bisailon (2018):

<https://mediumsaignant.media/comment-fonctionne-la-recommandation-musicale/>

cultural isolation of subscribers will have the effect of amplifying the bubble, reinforcing connections for artists who are aesthetically distant but geographically confined.

However, if filtering could rely on more descriptive data searchable by subscribers, the results it would produce could help open the bubble.

*“Stuck in a filter bubble? Unlike social networks, the use of streaming sites is more solitary and users seem more active in the choice of content to which they are exposed.”*¹⁰

If, on the contrary, the platforms offer content with little descriptive data, it should have the effect of narrowing down typical profiles (personæ) exploited by their algorithms at the risk of concentration around the most popular proposals.

If we can possibly interact with filter bubbles, change *playlist*, develop eclectic habits, depending on if we are a more or less proactive subscriber, it is obviously different for the artist who is dependent on a galaxy of similar artists that he has not chosen and cannot fine tune. Let us quote Pariser again: *echo chamber settings are invisible*. We don't know who we are in the eyes of the machine.

The question we are currently asking ourselves is whether it is possible from the point of view centered on artist, label and catalog, and secondly, from the point of view subscriber centered, to exercise better control over filter bubbles?

What is Enriched Music Metadata?

The metadata added in our BEFORE/AFTER example of zero iteration, which you will discover shortly, mostly falls into the enriched music metadata category. It will be the same for those of our experimental iterations. This is essentially information that is not yet considered mandatory for a title to be added to the platform's inventory.

Enriched metadata can take the following forms:

- Song lyrics and key words that enrich the works in terms of concepts evoked, places, themes, emotions, moods - information that feeds natural language query processing (natural language analysis processes or ALN);
- Words or expressions used to describe a genre, a style, a period, a movement, artistic influences, instruments heard;
- The list of contributors and their professions, studios where the recordings are created.
- Labels, other partners and rights holders¹¹ ;
- The key, the time signature, the tempo, the presence of samples ;
- The audiovisual synchro and advertising use of a song or even the awards won.

The enriched metadata cited above can potentially be delivered to services and may also be exposed in artists' official web pages in the form of structured data, microdata, *Rich Snippets*, Schema.org format, etc. These are therefore two large families of completely different best practices, without being incompatible: enriched metadata and structured microdata.

Connected speakers and voice assistants are largely used to launch playlists and musical pieces. We will soon be able to query the services in everyday language.

Google is in discussions with Spotify to allow its Gemini artificial intelligence to produce recommendations based on expressions linked to the genre, moods or lyrics of a song¹². This news constitutes the tip of the iceberg and it seems important to allow content producers to feed documentary databases with more enriched metadata than has been the case until now. This is why we have also launched, as part of this action research project, the initiative “Take back control of your musical emotions”¹³.

Certain standards, although little used, can allow the transmission of enriched data between producers, digital distributors and platforms¹⁴. It now seems useful to us to search the literature on the use of

¹⁰ See Villermet and colleagues, 2021.

¹¹ As such, it is possible to query Spotify by label, but this is a hidden function: label:"Motown"

¹² See this article regarding Gemini and Spotify:

<https://routenote.com/blog/googles-ai-gemini-hints-at-integration-with-spotify/>

¹³ See the proposed new Wikidata property:

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposal/Creative_work#music_mood

¹⁴ Par exemple DDEX-MEAD :

[https://kb.ddex.net/implementing-each-standard/media-enrichment-and-description-\(mead\)/](https://kb.ddex.net/implementing-each-standard/media-enrichment-and-description-(mead)/)

enriched metadata and concerning the good practices promoted by the platforms, in order to reconcile our work and industrial recommendations¹⁵. This work begins.

Zero iteration: BEFORE / AFTER Enriched Metadata Upgrade

The screenshots of the following pages show the effects of adding certain enriched metadata to the Web on the information offered by the knowledge panel generated by Google Search.

These additions are taken into account by the robots which optimize your SEO and generate the knowledge panel. They can, in the same way, be taken into account by the entire ecosystem of web pages and increase the discoverability of your artists. We have recently undertaken work to measure organic search results in response engines such as Google Search using technology [Hercules](#). We will come back to this.

On the other hand, we do not know to what extent, factually or admittedly, the online bases MusicBrainz and Wikidata - the Digital Commons - are used by online services. Tests are being carried out in this direction. We do know, however, that digital commons databases offer gateways between the different sites that present your artists and their music. Enriching them with your information could have a direct or indirect impact, the effects of which we are beginning to measure.

So far, the services claim that the enriched metadata available in the digital commons has not reached the critical mass that allows them to use it in their algorithms. Too many artists and information about them is absent. Generally speaking, platforms use little third-party data other than unique identifiers, values that are not contestable and very useful for reporting. On the other hand, nothing tells us to what extent the platforms do use commons data for exploratory purposes or to carry out certain checks.

For example, when performing organic searches in Google, enriched data seems to have an impact. The commons can play a role in consumer behavior which will then have a ricochet influence on the filter bubbles of streaming services.

One case was observed where, for the artist Sonido Pesao, the addition of the members of the collective and the name Heavy Sounds, their previous group, in the Wikidata aliases and MusicBrainz relationships would have had impacts. It was the only place where it was possible to create a link between musicians, their old and their new band in order to reconnect old and new fans.

In the following example, between BEFORE and AFTER, we added information in MusicBrainz and Wikidata. This information has been added to artists who are the subject of the zero iteration phase of our tests and which aims to establish a floor threshold for all the artists on which we work.

The exercise allows in certain cases to see the appearance of **Google side knowledge panel**¹⁶ previously absent or empty.

We have dedicated the year 2024 to implementing new enrichment iterations and observing the impacts. We will carry out measurements with an experimental cohort to which enriched metadata is added and a control cohort, whose artists have a profile and notoriety similar to the first, i.e. emerging artists under independent labels in France and Quebec, but on which we will not intervene in phases 1-2-3.

¹⁵ See this working document: [Métadonnées enrichies et bonnes pratiques | Littérature grise](#)

¹⁶ Review and question the use of quotation marks. BEFORE uses it, AFTER does not use it.

List of enriched metadata added during zero iteration

- Is this a group or a solo artist?
- Short description in French
- Short description in English
- IPI identifier (SACEM-SOCAN-ASCAP identifier)
- ISNI identifier (natural or legal person)
- Name
- First name (or group name)
- Start date of the activity (for a group)
- End date of the activity (for a group)
- Place of birth/foundation
- Date of death (if applicable, for a solo artist)
- Place of death (if applicable, for a solo artist)
- Alias or pseudonym
- AllMusic Link
- Amazon Link
- Apple Link
- Bandcamp Link
- BandsInTown Link
- Deezer ID
- Discogs Link
- Last.Fm Link
- MusicBrainz ID (MBID)
- Official website Link
- SongKick Link
- Soundcloud Link
- Spotify ID
- Wikidata ID (WKID)
- Wikipedia Link
- YouTube Link

BEFORE (August 7, 2023)

Google search results for "Everyday in June" (August 7, 2023). The search bar shows "Everyday in June" and the results are limited to 971,000 results in 0.37 seconds. The top result is an Instagram post from @everydayinjune, titled "Every Day In June! (@everydayinjune) • ...". Below the main result, there is a section for "Vidéos" (Videos) with four entries:

- Jordan Philippe à MEP - Clip EVERYDAY IN JUNE (YouTube · Caen la mer, 1 févr. 2023, 4:35)
- DAY 1 of outfits everyday in June #summeroutfits (YouTube · amyfuchsia, 1 juin 2023, 0:43)
- Welcome month of june 🌞🌞🌞 May everyday in June fill your ... (TikTok · velgem74, 31 mai 2023, 0:10)
- DAY 1 - 30 DAYS OF JUNE (YouTube · A Peek Inside, 1 juin 2020, 13:52)

A "Tout afficher" link is visible at the bottom of the video section.

AFTER (October 3, 2023) added rich metadata online, on Wikidata and MusicBrainz

Google search results for "everyday in june" (October 3, 2023). The search bar shows "everyday in june" and the results are limited to 2,240,000,000 results in 0.49 seconds. The top result is a YouTube channel page for "Every Day In June" (@everydayinjune5027133), which has 11 videos and 11 subscribers. Below this, there are Facebook and Instagram posts for "Every Day In June".

On the right side of the search results, there is a rich metadata section for "Every Day In June" (Clarinettiste). This section includes:

- An "Écouter" (Listen) section with links to YouTube, YouTube Music, Apple Music, and Deezer.
- An "Albums" section listing "Wall Of Sound".
- A "Titres" (Tracks) section listing several tracks: "Wall Of Sound", "Gathering Of The Spirits", "Noir De Jais", and "Ground Control To Major 7th", all from the album "Wall Of Sound · 2021".

Illustration: Google Search captures BEFORE and AFTER zero upgrade iteration

What role do Digital Commons play?

Currently, data from the music sector, the statistical production which supports the business intelligence of its industry, is essentially based on private application programming interfaces (APIs) developed by the platforms which control the provision of content and which are used by statistical services to collect data. This is the case for Chartmetric, SoundCharts, Music Tomorrow or InTempo Analytics. In the case of LUMINATE Data, commercial agreements for access to data are added, the terms of which we do not know.

The digital commons represent a public alternative allowing access to descriptive data that can facilitate the discernment of artists which precedes the production of usage and listening statistics. The best known are MusicBrainz, Wikidata, but also Discogs, AllMusic (both public and proprietary) or IMDb (for cinema and therefore for soundtracks) and a number of other open and sometimes linked databases, such as for example the bases of national libraries and the register of artists offered by the ISNI database¹⁷.

As we have seen, online services claim that the enriched metadata available in the digital commons have not reached the critical mass that allows them to use it in their algorithms. There is a lack of too many artists and information about them.

However, we know that they offer gateways between different sites and that enriching them with your information can only have a direct or indirect positive impact, the extent of which we will not yet measure.

Our current research work focuses on the effects of efforts made towards digital commons databases which, in our eyes, constitute a new public agora that can contribute, in part, to the safeguarding of cultural heritage.

One of our hypotheses is that the absolute takeover of the distribution networks of cultural goods by the information technology sector can be rebalanced by the existence of this type of public spaces.

Streaming services, recommendation systems and echo chambers

The daily number of new tracks added to Spotify [now reaches 100,000](#) and there is no indication that this figure could be reduced, on the contrary¹⁸.

Given the growing number of content ingested and offered by digital online listening platforms (DOLP) or streaming platforms (*Digital Service Provider* or DSP), discoverability is also becoming an issue for them. They are constantly looking for improvements to their recommendation systems and their editorial playlists.¹⁹

To better understand this, a few interviews took place, notably with two of the key players in the streaming offering (Deezer and Spotify). These conversations allow us to put forward the hypothesis that online services are open to the idea of more systematic exchanges with those involved in content supply.

When questioned about the apparent flaws in their systems in terms of findability and recommendation, they point to the lack of documentation provided to them as the main cause, both in terms of enriched metadata and administrative metadata. As such, they highlight the difficulty of associating original works and their various sound recordings, the possibility of which would make it possible to produce more compliant accounting statements. Our interviews revealed that their conversations with rights management collectives and labels, in order to obtain ISWC identifiers for musical works, have so far met with failure. This type of prerogative would represent either an apprehended threat to business models or even an overload of work whose benefits we do not anticipate.

The platforms consider that open data sources do not offer the authoritative and critical mass of information which allows them to remedy this situation or to draw the necessary material to better feed their algorithms. As a result, service recommendation processes always rely largely on social consumption data produced in their own ecosystems and according to their rules.

¹⁷ See, for example, the list of artistic contributors linked to Céline Dion: <https://isni.org/isni/0000000073642195>

¹⁸ An industrial context document was produced by Vincent Castaignet and is available for consultation:

[W1.1.1 Contexte de l'industrie de la musique](#)

¹⁹ Issue expressed in particular during the Conference — *What place for creators in online culture?* held on November 15, 2022 - <https://pcen.fr/activites/colloque-quelle-place-pour-les-createurs-dans-la-culture-en-ligne>

As a corollary, record companies and music labels have difficulty attracting the attention of music lovers to their artists who are likely to appeal. They have difficulty ensuring that their productions are cutting through this overabundance of supply and that they are adequately offered to the right subscribers.

In terms of content packaging, they can rely, on a case-by-case basis, on the dashboards provided by artist services (e.g. Spotify for Artists or Deezer for Creators) and certain features offered by digital distributor dashboards (e.g. Believe Backstage). These environments nevertheless allow the entry of relatively few fields of information.

The new law on digital broadcasting in Canada works to put in place a framework that forces streaming services to support production (through a form of tax or financial contribution), but also the promotion of varied content and their discoverability through the introduction of technical measures.

At the moment, recommendation technologies based primarily on collaborative filtering and which are based on the tastes of subscribers who are similar to you, should in principle promote discoverability. But if no new opening is offered, they can gradually lead to a concentration on artists statistically obtaining a better popularity score or located in a geographical area bordering yours.

Activating the levers of discoverability aims to break through or disrupt this phenomenon of concentration. These actions must be enriched by new good practices to reduce the harmful effects and biases of algorithms and they respond to the challenge of encouraging greater diversity in listening, of making it possible to cross the geographical or psychological borders which lock listeners into their bubble.

In parallel, industrial research is currently being conducted in Quebec and aims to measure the relative weight of subscribers' active listening over algorithmic listening, i.e. the notion of **provenance**, for a circumscribed catalog and to measure the gap between organic practice and recommendations. These studies reveals what appears to be a biased ratio between the actual tastes of subscribers and their editorial treatment ²⁰.

Illustration: LUMINATE Date at SXSW 2023
42% of the 158 million tracks available have 10 plays or fewer.

Results to date

Our project underwent pre-testing in the summer of 2022, using the Spotify's Get Recommendations API and was able to see that the recommendations made for an artist and a starting title (Seed Artist and Seed Track) were similar, regardless of the listening history or the location of the subscriber (and the identification token thereof — *Token*). We summarily conclude that it is always collaborative filtering,

²⁰ See the APEM project [“Provenance of listening to Quebec music on streaming platforms”](#)

with regard to a given territory, which essentially defines the distance between two titles. That is to say, how many times track Y has been listened to by subscribers who have listened to track X.

Other summary results arise from the preparations which will make it possible to measure the effects of the enrichment work. We note that the inventory of enriched metadata available and exposed in the digital commons is meager and varies greatly from one label to another.

We established an initial digital commons optional metadata richness score for artists in our first cohort. We were able to see that the state of the initial BEFORE documentation was richer for Quebec artists than for French artists. We can deduce as an explanation for this that awareness of the use of metadata has been underway for some time in Quebec, particularly through the ADISQ training cycle on discoverability.²¹

That said, the models, ontologies (lists of data deemed important) and controlled vocabularies (“repositories” citing the standardized terms to use) are still not mature. Let’s take the example of what we call “moods”: e.g. happy, energetic, calm, etc. Our research matrix currently identifies 68 moods²² sometimes used by DDEX, Cyanite, Simbals, AllMusic, etc. However, as for the international standard DDEX-MEAD, the humors are only listed in English and do not offer multilingual translation. It only gives definitions for the 5 moods which are Dark, Happy, Mellow, Romantic and Sad. At the start of our work, the Wikidata database did not allow us to identify moods associated with a sound recording and we had to work with its community to have the property recognized.

Currently, the only public database that allows you to consult and contribute to the moods associated with a sound recording is AllMusic, but this information is systematically absent for French-speaking pieces.²³

Thus, we understand that platforms cannot build new recommendation functionalities if the critical mass of information required is not there. It is possible that only labels which have specific and substantial resources, allowing them to adopt new best practices, will succeed in complying with the standards of the streaming industry.

Method

Our method for measuring the effects of metadata enrichment is freely inspired by the theory of falsifiability (Popper, 1935)²⁴ which consists of formulating a singular statement (i.e. not multiplying causality tests in parallel) in such a way that it is possible to demonstrate its veracity until the day it is proven that it is no longer so.

We will take the following statements as an example:

- A. Adding a referential artistic influence (**Follower of (P1775)**) for an artist in Wikidata increases their findability on a platform like Spotify.
- B. Increasing the findability of an artist helps increase their number of plays.
- C. Increasing the number of listens to an artist encourages the opening of their echo chamber to new geographic markets.

To succeed in successively falsifying these assertions, we must put in place a method that will test what we know or think we know about discoverability. We will have to apply our method to concrete cases and submit these cases to tests. We will determine the method with which we will verify the veracity of a statement such as that of the addition of a referential artistic influence in the Wikidata commons.

Our ultimate goal is **to decide whether or not to add a better business practice** who would argue that taking this action is useful for artists or labels.

We must set ourselves **general results objectives** : (for example) **enrich the relationships of similar artists** to burst through the echo chamber. Similar artists are essentially determined by collaborative filtering and used by the platforms to produce “Artist Radio” – or playlists that start with a given artist.

²¹ Training created by our collaborators Jacynthe Plamondon and Sylvain Picard:

<https://adisq.cultive.ca/students/catalog/656-decouvrabilite-partie-1-les-metadonnees-montreal-cours-hybride-07-septembre-2023-presente-par-adisq>

²² Mood matrix:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1aOulQU-TP6w2zPI0wEKfTkSqXD9f2WyoMr85QslvLGY/edit?usp=sharing>

²³ See the example of “L’hymne à l’amour” performed by Édith Piaf at the closure ceremony of the 2024 Olympic Games : <https://www.allmusic.com/song/lhymne-%C3-lamour-mt0036251260#moodsThemes>

²⁴ “The distinctive character of empirical statements lies (...) in the fact that they can be criticized and supplanted by better ones.” (Popper, 1935, p.46).

As we have already pointed out, similar artists represent the contours of an echo chamber. The objectives of our tests, carried out with the assistance of artists and labels, aim to bring new variables into play on the lists of similar artists.

For example, we set ourselves a specific **objective** of **bringing artist X closer to artist Y** to enrich the affinity links of X with various artists Y from neglected markets.

We have formed a first cohort of France-Quebec tests with the aim of encouraging the opening of the bubble. In the coming months and according to this same logic, we will establish other artistic pairs and test which actions and enriched metadata promote the opening of the bubble.

For our first cohort of artists, we first carried out a zero iteration, a first phase of upgrading the basic information in Wikidata and in MusicBrainz, so that this information is equally provided for everyone. Find the list of these basic fields in the BEFORE / AFTER section (above).

Randomized experiments

We then undertook a series of randomized experiments (or randomized trials) to attempt to measure a causal correlation associated with the addition of enriched metadata.

We point out that our hypothesis is **Currently** very low, since as we have verified, the platforms claim not to use this documentation to power their algorithms.

Nevertheless, we considered that the work of setting up such tests constituted a gain for long-term research allowing us to debate options, parameters, which could be applicable in an evolving future gradually taking this metadata into account.

Our iterations for these tests 1-3 are based on collaboration with the artists and labels concerned, in particular with the support of our field research partner InTempo in Quebec and with La FÉLIN, the association of independent labels for France. A monitoring protocol is put in place.

Test Artists – Cohort 1

A matrix of our work presents the fields that we have enriched for a set of cohorts of artists and labels. Here are the cohorts of test artists who have undergone the zero iteration phase (upgrade of basic metadata). This is followed by the breakdown of these artists into two cohorts, with regard to the enrichment tests that we have conducted in the spring and summer of 2024. Find **in neon pink the artists of the experimental groups** And **in gray, those of the control groups**.

Quebec	France	Reference	Genre
Elage Diouf	Star Feminine Band	Cheikh Lo	mexpand
Sylvain Picard	Black Octave	Fire! Chatterton	New Song
Geneviève Racette	H-Burns	Sharon Van Etten	indie people
Shout	Danakil		
Stick & Bow	Lucile Boulanger		
Christine Tassan	Cissy Street		

Test Artists – Cohort 2

Quebec	France	Reference	Genre
Heavy Sound	Slumb	Thievery Corporation	Latin electronic
Samuel	Léonie Pernet	Ani DiFranco	folk rock
The north wind	My shoes are red	Tri Yann	Celtic folk music
Jacques Kuba Séguin	Everyday in June		
Lakes of Canada	Laetitia Sheriff		
Mehdi Cayenne	Sad Animal		

Workspaces (in french)

- [MATRICE | Enrichissement des données | Vocabulaire contrôlé](#)
 - [MATRICE | Points de données | Outils de mesure de découvrabilité](#)
 - [MATRICE | Données brutes](#)
 - [* MATRICE | Résultats et graphes](#)
- Looker Studio : https://hercules.report/fr/data_engine_queries
InTempo Analytics portal: <http://analytics.intempomusique.com/>
- [Alimentation données et captures](#) (InTempo file)

The chosen artists all work on behalf of independent labels. They are paired by freestyle affinities. They did not maintain professional relations with each other before the start of the work.

The artists of Cohort 1 share in their **Clusters** from the **Music Tomorrow** service a reference artist assigned to them - while those of Cohort 2 were freely assigned a reference artist, initially having no artists in common.

For each artist which are the subject of these tests, we have created master folders which will ultimately contain:

- a shared space at the Bridge.audio file sharing service;
- screenshots of organic searches in Google Search;
- .csv and .xls files which present their *Clusters* defined by Music Tomorrow;
- .xls files which present their similar artists and the degrees of separation observed between them (3 levels), the popularity and the number of “followers” of each, longitudinally using the InTempo Analytics software (*Artists relationships history*);
- an analytical logbook of efforts already made and recommended for the future including responses to the qualitative questionnaire concerning artistic affinities and classic marketing actions planned for the first half of 2024;
- weekly statistical readings of general rank data, number of monthly Spotify listens and Deezer fans made in the Chartmetric service.

These master files are shared with the artists and their teams and constitute the basis on which we base our work in the months and years to come and to keep track of it.

Thus, we will also share our project space on Bridge.audio ([Echo Chamber Research Project](#)) with artists or stakeholders wishing to follow our work to enrich the documentation (contact iconoclastejr@gmail.com).

Experimental enrichment iterations

After carrying out the zero iteration, we questioned the labels concerned in order to target the enrichment work that we implemented in 2024.

This questionnaire was accompanied by interviews with the labels and aimed to identify an enrichment strategy which fits adequately into the actions already taken by them.

Enrichment actions respond to an imperative that we impose on ourselves in order to be consistent with the France-Quebec Strategy on the discoverability of cultural content online, that is to say that **we work in the spirit of making comparisons between France and Quebec**.

To do this, we created affinity connections between French and Quebec artists. These connections, like the choice of cohort artists, were made in a more or less directed manner by the research team. Artistic affinities are a very subjective variable and we will take this into account when interpreting our future results.

In order to meet our specific objective which is to bring artist levels of separation by carrying distinct iterations (degree by degree), we have defined a common reference artist for each pair of testing artists.

Our research also established the prerogative that artists and labels would not invest in paid advertising and audience targeting campaigns. We study organic discoverability based on documentation and metadata only.

We could perhaps one day consider measuring the effects of **combined interactions** between documentation, advertising purchasing and field activities, but this involves the use of very complex dynamic systems and beyond our reach.

Iteration 1 – Artistic influences

We agreed to base iteration 1 on the association of test cohorts, with **reference** artists of their corresponding genres and aesthetics. We chose to qualify three variables in this sense, namely those of a territory of origin, a genre as defined in Wikidata and a **notable influence**, recognized as a standard for this given aesthetic family.

HOW :

Define the artists in the test and control groups. The artists of our cohort 1 and 2 who decided on their influences when conducting our survey for this purpose constitute the test group and those who did not comment are our control group.

We added a Wikidata item for Music Tomorrow (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q126372732>).

We use Music Tomorrow Clusters (Audience Builder > top_artists.csv) by identifying an artist common to France and Quebec pairs.

We made an enrichment of metadata associated with artistic influences using the Wikidata property [Follower of \(P1775\)](#) as a constraint of qualifier of a declaration from **Genre (P136)** (see [list of Wikidata genres](#)) for our relatively unknown artists who work in the manner of a recognized artist. Our 12 artists in the test group and their 6 reference artists are associated with a genre consistent with the Wikidata genre list.

We added the property of [workplace \(P937\)](#) (France or Quebec), for all artists.

MEASURES :

Carry out measurements on various **data points (factors)** in the months following these additions. For this iteration, these will be the data points delivered in the basic .csv files of the Chartmetric service - Added in MATRIX 2 data points and screenshots of organic searches in Google Search - Added in the master folders .

Wikidata (WD) PUSH DONE: June 17, 2024

Iteration 2 – Works and sound recordings

WHY :

While several statistics are produced for performing artists, royalty reports and playlists are based on specific tracks appearing in their catalogs. Various qualitative data, such as genre or mood, are established on tracks and not on the artist as a whole. We therefore agreed to establish a trifecta of witness works and corresponding recordings to carry out certain tests.

HOW :

Having recourse to **Quick Statements** to add data in batch to Wikidata, we added **3 works** (or musical compositions Q105543609) by artist from the exploratory group of cohorts 1 and 2 - then enriched the metadata associated with them including the ISWC ([P1827](#)) (<https://iswcnet.cisac.org/search> - Added the matching **3 sound recordings** piece of music with singing [Q55850593](#) or instrumental [Q55850643](#) and their corresponding ISRC (P1243), according to the official ISRC search source from IFPI (<https://isrcsearch.ifpi.org/>). We completed with the year of recording (P10135), the year of publication (P577), the language of the work (P407) and the discographic label (P264).

MusicBrainz (MB) PUSH DONE: June 17, 2024

Wikidata PUSH DONE: August 23, 2024

Iteration 3 – Moods and emotions

WHY :

Moods and the theory of emotions involve the definition of a controlled frame of reference allowing this characteristic to be qualified for a sound recording (*tracks/tracks*).

It is still very difficult to contribute to and publicly source the musical moods associated with a sound recording. Some paid services offer file analysis tools using artificial intelligence, but there are very few places where it is possible to source the mood of a musical piece, report it to the public or the industrial value chain by sharing URLs.

Artists and labels are helpless in the face of this descriptive challenge. The sample moods used in our Wikidata property proposal were aligned with the AllMusic mood list to allow to source moods that are the subject of Wikidata declarations. However, French-speaking artists are absent from AllMusic as we have seen in particular with the example from “L’hymne à l’amour” popularized by Edith Piaf and Celine Dion's flagship performance at the closing of the 2024 Olympic Games.

In order to source the mood we used the French service provider Bridge.audio and its automatic calculation service using artificial intelligence. However, this information is not visible online, except for the holder of a free Bridge.audio account. To upload the files to a project for analysis, we had to obtain a digitized copy of the audio file, since URL mood analysis is not currently available. To speed up this procedure, we purchased the files from the iTunes Store. To add the mood to Wikidata, we had to proceed without being able to meet the condition of adding a public source reference, which could lead to possible rejection.

The meaning we give to the mood variable is that of expressing feelings in everyday language which will make it possible to signal listening desires to a service which generates musical lists on demand. Our approach implies that documentation is established in an *artist-centric* manner by the artist or his label. This way of conceiving moods differs from approaches to the effect that music triggers listeners

emotions (*user-centric*) who perceives it as joyful, energetic or other (Delbouys et al., 2018; Hu and Downie, 2010; Juslin and Laukka, 2004; Russell, 1989; Saari et al., n. d.; Song et al., 2012; Zentner et al., 2008).

We will therefore seek to qualify and observe moods as an intrinsic property that we will associate with a recording as would be the case for other descriptive metadata. We have also chosen to use standardized adjectives to proceed.

Connected speakers make it possible to request music based on mood criteria and it will soon be possible to generate and save playlists using instructions (*prompts*) formulated in natural language to services.

We had to define a list of prescriptive moods knowing it is a very subjective exercise and moreover, that the subjective meaning given to the terms will be decisive when translating them into languages other than English. It is also not clear how much weight to give to each music and text when it comes to associating a mood with an audio track (Hu and Downie, 2010).

Wikidata provides the “Theme” property ([P921](#)) to describe a subject addressed and which can allow the addition of a state of mind (for example “melancholy”) to an artistic work. On the other hand, this digital common does not offer any specific property describing [a mood associated with music](#) (Wikidata Music Project), a state of mind, a feeling, an atmosphere, a “mood”, a “feeling”.

In areas other than music, Wikidata makes use of the Robert Plutchik's theory of emotions²⁵ ([Q9415](#)) based on the use of common nouns, but for its part, the music industry rather bases the use of *moods* on the use of adjectives.

The candidate for the international standard DDEX-MEAD (Media Enrichment and Description) which offers 27 moods^{26 27}, has to date only defined 5 of them: Dark, Happy, Mellow, Romantic and Sad. DDEX, which represents the industrial consortium of major players in sound recording and online music services, held a plenary on April 15, 2024 (plenary *Maintaining Auxiliary Allowed Value Sets*) during which it did not rule on its skills, and its continuation or not, of the work surrounding the values taken into account by the MEAD model.

As for itself, the theory of humors of Antiquity (Hippocrates) schematically put forward 4 families of humors, associated with the elements of nature, and which freely correspond to the DDEX humors, i.e. **calm-mellow** (Downbeat), **energetic-energetic** (Upbeat)²⁸, **happy-happy** And **sad-sad**. This seems to us to constitute a general starting point which is still plausible (consult the visual summary that we offer below).

Note that the moods **calm** And **energetic** can be assimilated to musical notions such as tempo or the density of arrangements (what Russell (1989) classifies as intensity), while adjectives **happy** And **sad** are clearly feelings that Russell classed as the affective valence between pleasure and displeasure.

²⁵ <https://www.6seconds.org/2022/03/13/plutchik-wheel-emotions/>

²⁶ https://service.ddex.net/dd/DD-AVS-001/dd/avs_Mood.html

²⁷ [DDEX-MEAD | Revue de littérature](#)

²⁸ See the Moodplaylist service: <https://www.moodplaylist.it/>

Illustration: Russell's circular model of affects (« a circumplex model of affect »)

(Feldman Barrett, L., & Russell, J.A., 1998).

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Figure-1-Russells-Circumplex-model-of-affect_fig1_290496626

There are thus a multitude of lists of moods and we have aggregated one freely which was submitted to the [Wikidata community and its Music project](#)²⁹ for debate.

Various services offer classification of moods by automatic analysis supported by artificial intelligence. Let us mention Disco.io and Bridge.audio (a French service) which work from the ingestion of audio files. Then Cyanite.ai which uses a YouTube URL or the audio file. The moods supported by Cyanite are: Aggressive, Calm, Chill, Dark, Energetic, Epic, Ethereal, Happy, Romantic, Sad, Scary, Sexy, Uplifting.

Cyanite offers a multiple-value mood graph, using its terminology of 13 values and which varies depending on the tracks analyzed. Thus the mood of a room offers weighting according to 8 axes whose values vary on a scale from 0.00 to 0.99.

We have produced a definition for the chosen moods and have requested the creation of a new Wikidata declarative property³⁰ for moods associated with music, before carrying out enrichments and tests³¹.

²⁹ See the Wikidata “Music” project: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Music

³⁰ See the preparatory document: [Propriété Émotions | Wikidata:WikiProject_Music](#)

³¹ A preliminary validation of this track relating to moods could be done with the help of Vincent Castaignet, Matthias Robine (simbals) or Geoffroy Peeters (IRCAM).

Finally, we are opening up the possibility of shortly associating adjectives linked to moods in the MetaMusic project documentation tool.

HOW :

We chose to create a new Wikidata property in consultation with its user community. The proposal was adopted by the community on June 17, 2024: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P12830>

It is possible to consult the argument of the proposal in the "Discussion" tab" of the new property. We established the conversation with Moebeus and Dmitriy from the Wikidata:WikiProject_Music project on Telegram to support us in the creation of the new property (May 2024).

The work also consisted of defining a list of adjectives associated with moods for Wikidata (Q) in order to qualify the new property (P). We will constrain the association of the "Moods" property in Wikidata³² to the elements that are the "music track with singing" (Q55850593) or instrumental (Q55850643).

The property's talk page offers examples for the moods considered for this initial phase https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property_talk:P12830

We have identified a procedure based on AllMusic to source the mood of the songs <https://www.allmusic.com/song/born-to-run-mt0000187785#moodsThemes> which consists of carrying out a search by title and consulting the associated moods.

It will nevertheless be very difficult to source the mood of the recordings for the artists in our cohorts in AllMusic given their low notoriety and the almost systematic absence of French-speaking titles in this database. We have currently opted to use Bridge.audio's artificial intelligence to auto-calculate moods, but it is not possible to offer a public URL pointing to the mood lists of the tracks. We will thus be able, for lack of anything better, to declare moods without source, waiting for the community or industry to react.

We added enriched metadata associated with the moods of our test sound recordings and performed correlation measurements via queries in Hercules and Looker Studio formed as follows: "Energy" playlist.

Wikidata PUSH COMPLETED: August 23, 2024

³² See the conversation about creating a new property: [Wikidata:Property proposals](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposals)

Illustration: Deezer Flow, an algorithm that allows interaction with our moods

Illustration: Wheel of Emotions by Robert Plutchik

List of enriched metadata added during iterations 1, 2 and 3

- works (3 by experimental artist) / (**compositions musicales** Q105543609), their **ISWC** (P1827) and [form of work](#) (P7937) (ex. chanson)
- sound recordings (3 per experimental artist) and their **ISRC** (P1243) / **music track with vocals** [Q55850593](#) or **music track without lyrics** [Q55850643](#))
- **year of registration** (P10135) (sourced via IFPI)
- **year of publication** (~~P577~~) (unavailable)
- artistic influence stallion **follower of** (P1775)
- affinity artistic influence **influenced by (affinity)** (P737)
- **genre** (P136)
- **workplace** (France or Quebec) (P937)
- **language of the work** (P407)
- **record label** (P264)
- we created the property **musical mood** ([P12830](#)) and enriched this information by virtue of 10 variables:
 - energetic (Q126271501)
 - happy (Q126207699)
 - romantic (Q126272565)
 - enthusiast (Q126596716)
 - aggressive (Q126274660)
 - sombre (Q126275248)
 - triste (Q126275836)
 - calm (Q126276136)
 - ethereal (Q128693101)
 - nostalgic (Q128693144)

Dashboard and new results measures

Following the implementation of our enrichment protocols, we explored the implementation of periodic automatic protocols for measuring effects and results.

A first prototype of a dynamic results visualization space is created by A10S-Hercules:

<https://lookerstudio.google.com/u/0/reporting/f249d7c2-7951-41fa-83eb-d961bb0f35bd/page/FU1UE>

If it persists, efforts will be carried out jointly by InTempo, A10S (Hercules) and LATICCE. We will add the raw data collected in InTempo Analytics³³ Google Search, ULYSS, a meta-recommendation conversational robot project created by LATICCE and in Beta-Testing phase with the UQAM student community, as well as the Chartmetric statistics aggregation service.

We have developed a basket of requests which can evolve, for listening lists targeted at the artists of the first two French and Quebec cohorts and the moods (mood) associated with their sound recordings.

The Clusters of the Music Tomorrow firm, offered by the function *Audience Builder* allowed us to draw up lists of similar artists and to make our choices of common standard artists by analyzing the aesthetic clusters calculated for each of the test artists.

In the early phases of this aggregation work, our metrics for iterations 1-3 focused on overall growth in CM Artist Rank, Spotify Monthly Listeners and Deezer Fans engagement, expansion of similar artists lists, the rapprochement between the paired artists and their common standard artist.

We are aiming to produce the first results for the end of the project supported by the Franco-Québécoise Mission on the digital discoverability of French-speaking cultural content.

³³ On November 27, 2024, for security reasons, Spotify for Developers announced a reduction in access to its APIs which will have consequences on the capabilities of this product to harvest data:
<https://developer.spotify.com/blog/2024-11-27-changes-to-the-web-api>

Best business practices to implement

It seems that only the voluntary efforts of labels and artists aware of the long-term potential of enriching the description of their works and sound recordings is currently possible.

We nevertheless draw the reader's attention to the service **MetaMusic**, a field partner in our project, which launched in 2024 an online space for capturing, archiving and sharing metadata from sound recordings and industry players. This is a site offered by a Canadian consortium, but which can accommodate foreign declarations³⁴.

It is not possible to impose best metadata enrichment business practices at the moment of content production unless industrial policies in this sense are supported by professional associations or imposed by grant programs. However, these would be political measures which have not yet been seen.

Nevertheless, our research is committed in a long term perspective to the measure of the impact of enriched metadata endeavors, to validate discoverability action taking and share our findings with all stakeholders, including platforms.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we will repeat that the discoverability variable in a marketing strategy for music is still a poorly marked territory. The definition of discoverability and its different meanings must still be clarified, particularly with regard to the effects sought from the angle of the actors concerned, whether artists or subscribers. Digital services, for their part, deploy two-sided strategies focused on both artists and users.

We are continuing our work seeking to validate that the activation of discoverability, using digital documentation enriched with cultural content, constitutes an avenue that complements traditional marketing efforts or paid audience targeting.

Already we believe in the importance of encouraging dialog between platforms and independent labels with the aim of upgrading the experience of streaming service subscribers for the mutual benefit of all parties in the new technical music industry ecosystem.

We would like to highlight the work underway at the Quebec Ministry of Culture and Communications with identifying the provisions that a right to discoverability of French-speaking content could adopt in the legislation (Beaudoin et al. 2024). We place our work in this logic and invite the reader to consult the recommendations produced by LATICCE as part of these debates in Appendix A of this report.

We support the idea that competition will soon be between labels that apply good business practices, that manage to provide enriched metadata to the value chain, and those that do not.

We support the idea of incentivizing platforms to enable algorithm interactions with subscribers, enabling discoveries based on aesthetic or qualitative information provided by labels, music creators and artists.

We believe that the overly concentrated usurpation by non-human actors of recommendation, of roles previously held by humans, impoverishes the experience of musical listening.

Within the limits of our resources, we intend to continue our action research work to measure the positive and negative effects of these technologies on the choices available to the public.

³⁴ <https://portail.metamusique.ca/Account/Login/>

APPENDIX A – Public consultations

LATICCE participated in calls for comments from Canadian and Quebec legislators in connection with the recent or future introduction of public policies to promote discoverability.

We invite the reader to consult our interventions which include the following recommendations:

1. (Fairness) The law must allow a local work to be treated fairly compared to its peers produced in other states.
2. (Remuneration) The law must provide that the royalty sharing mechanisms established by the platforms are fair for Quebec artists and producers, in particular by using user-centered remuneration approaches.
3. (Discoverability) The law must provide for obligations for the presentation of content, particularly in terms of optimizing content search criteria.
4. (Transparency) The law must require platforms to produce discoverability reports for local products, especially French-speaking and independent.
5. (Monitoring measures) The law must provide for three levels of reflection and governance and a neutral and collaborative authority to ensure monitoring: (1) a hybrid Forum allowing cooperation between specialists and laypeople and responsible for monitoring and formulation issues; (2) a dedicated research center in partnership allowing the validation of the issues; (3) a discoverability Nudge Unit serving as an incentive space for producing tools aimed at activating discoverability.
6. (Metadata) As a prerequisite, the law must encourage producers, artists and creators to ensure the presence of basic metadata. For productions made with public funds, this should be mandatory. Metadata must be aligned with international sectoral standards and Quebec repositories must be aligned with semantic standards for structured and linked data.
7. (Norms and standards) Quebec must be represented at industrial tables that adopt international standards.
8. (Consumption statistics) The law must provide for the statistical standards to be implemented to validate compliance with and the effects of the law and thus mandate the OCCQ to measure consumption. The methodology for identifying Quebec content must be aligned with the CRTC's definition of French-speaking vocal music.

Rioux, M., Wells, G.-P., Simeu, B. A. and Bisailon, J.-R. (2024, July 8). Legislative framework relating to the discoverability of French-speaking cultural content - LATICCE brief to the Ministry of Culture and Communications of Quebec. LATICCE (CEIM-UQAM).

https://consultation.quebec.ca/rails/active_storage/blobs/redirect/eyJfcmFpbHMiOnsibWVzc2FnZSI6IkJBaHBBCjlrIiwilZlhwIjpuZDlWxsLjJwdXliOiJibG9iX2lkIn19--d558d3d7bd08d23292e6a208e3d6a4956a47471e/LATICCE%20Consultation%20publique%20sur%20la%20loi%20D%C3%A9couvrabilit%C3%A9.pdf

LATICCE brief for public consultations (CRTC 2023-138), (2023, July 11)

<https://applications.crtc.gc.ca/DocWebBroker/OpenDocument.aspx?DMID=4412597>

APPENDIX B – Spotify's Legal Actions

The Spotify platform may wish to be excluded from the obligations provided for by Bill C-11.

Spotify and the Digital Media Association in Washington are advocating for self-regulation and refusing the imposition of rules based on the definition of public policies emanating from parliaments³⁵.

Thus, the establishment of consultation processes, of collaborative governance (Emerson and Nabatchi 2015) within the industry and with the platforms, on the question of discoverability regulation seems jeopardized, as long as legal actions are in progress.

³⁵ See the DIMA publication of July 4, 2024:

<https://dima.org/news-and-resources/dima-statement-on-streaming-services-legal-challenge-against-crtc/>

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